

Improving crop harvest Index for optimal rice production on tidal swampland

Salwati^{1*}, Lutfi Izhar¹ and Yardha¹

¹Jambi Assessment Institute for Agricultural Technology (AIAT)

*Corresponding author: salwatijbi@yahoo.com

ABSTRACT

The study was carried out to get the optimum technology of tidal swamplands for rice farming sustainability, increase in Planting Index (PI), some adaptive cultivars in tidal swamplands and assess the effect of land salinity to support rice PI. The experiment was conducted in Simbur Naik tidal land areas, Jambi, from February to November of 2014. A split-plot design with three replications was arranged for the field experiment. Main plot were Amelioration and fertilization (M), consisted of M1. Cultivation techniques used by farmers, M2. No-tillage with inputs (washing + lime 3 t ha⁻¹ + fertilizer), M3. Minimum tillage with input (washing+ lime 3 t ha⁻¹+ husk 3 t ha⁻¹ + ZnSO₄ + fertilizer). Sub Plot were rice varieties (V); V1. Sintanur, V2. Inpara 1, V3. Inpara 2, V4. Inpara 4, V5. Inpara 5. The observations were: 1) Analysis of soil physical and chemical properties of the experimental site before planting and after harvesting, 2) Plants growing, 3) grain yield and yield components, 4) intensity of the green color of the leaves (21, 35, 49 and 63 days after planting), 5) analysis of NPK nutrients in grain and straw. Multiple regression analysis showed that there was highly significant component effect on grain yield; the amount of total grain, the grain emptiness, and the weight of filled grains of 1000, where these three outcome components were also influenced by the treatment given by Amelioration. Some of the varieties were tested have different yields. The highest grain yield was Inpara 4 of 3.42 t / ha, followed by Inpara 2 of 2.89 t/ha DUP, while Inpari 1 showed a higher response for tidal land improvements, there were differences in responses between varieties. Although that was not statistically significant, the amelioration was affected to the growth of rice, but the provision of husk and the addition of ZnSO₄ were not affect the tidal rice.

Keywords: tidal swamps, rice fields, harvest index, jambi

INTRODUCTION

Pressure to maintain and increase the capacity of Indonesian rice production system arises from the excessive increasingly rate of rice irrigated land conversion, especially in Java. Moreover, the threat of climate change phenomenon, mainly due to rising air temperature and drought stress, flood, salinity, etc.

It's narrowness of fertile rice fields. Generality, in Java Island, rice areas has shifted to non-agricultural use or non-food production. Likewise, alternative rice development can be directed totidal swampy rice fields. In tidal agroecosystems, rice can be cultivated mainly on potential land typology, narrow acid sulfate soil and shallow peat soil which can be utilized as wet rice field or with surjan system.

Tidal swamp land area in Indonesia was about 20.1 million ha, about 9.53 million ha has potential to be used as agricultural activities and has been reclaimed about 4.18 million ha. However, there are constraints faced in tidal swamp areas for agricultural practices such as low fertility status, biophysical land characterized by nutrient deficiency, high acidity, Al, Fe and H₂S injuring and salinity contagion (Sarwani et al. 1994; Najib and Fahmi, 2010).

Innovation for rice production technology supporting production improvement program in tidal swamp land has been available, such as land preparation technological innovation, superior use of rice varieties and others. With this purpose, research was aimed to: 1) test and get the optimum technology for tidal swamp land for sustainable rice farming and increasing Harvest Indeks (HI), 2) get some adaptive rice varieties in tidal and salinity-affected areas to support increasing HI.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The study was carried out in Tidal swampy land of Simbur Naik, East Tanjung Jabung region, Jambi Province. The demonstration areas were on farmer's rice field during planting season of 2014. The field experiment was arranged in split-plot design as follows:

Main plots were Amelioration and Fertilization (M);

M1. Cultivation techniques commonly conducted by farmers

M2. Without ground treatment (TOT) with input (washing + lime 3 t ha⁻¹ + fertilizer)

M3. Minimum ground exercise with input (washing + lime 3 t ha⁻¹+ 3 t ha⁻¹ husk charcoal + ZnSO₄ + fertilizer)

Sub plots were rice varieties (V);

V1. Sintanur

V2. Inpara 1

V3. Inpara 2

V4. Inpara 4

V5. Inpara 5

Applications of fertilizer were 90, 40 and 40 kg ha⁻¹ of N, P₂O₅ and K₂O, respectively. Nitrogen was obtained from Urea-Phonska around 110-265 kg ha⁻¹ (according to local availability). Phonska was applied at 10 Days After Planting

(DAP), whereas Urea applied at 30 and 45 DAP (50% of each dose). The treatment was conducted in 8 × 6 m² plot area and repeated 3 times. Plant spacing was 20 cm × 20 cm. The soil sample was taken after harvesting of the first planting season to investigate the residual effects of amelioration. Pest controlling was carried out intensively.

The observations were conducted on:

- 1). Analysis of physical and chemical properties of soil experimental site, before planting and after harvesting.
- 2). Plant height and number of tillers, calculated from 12 clumps per experimental plot, p every 2 weeks from 21 to 77 DAP.
- 3). The intensity of green leaf color was observed on 21, 35, 49 and 63 DAP.
- 4). Early flowering and harvesting time was recorded from each plot.
- 5). One day before harvesting component of 12 clumps per trial plot were taken and the number of panicles, the number and weight of grain content and hollow, and grain water content were calculated
- 6). Rice harvesting was taken from 2x4 m² (200 clumps) per experiment plot, and after threshing the total weight of grain and grain water content were calculated. Filled grain and water content were also calculated.
- 7). Nutrient analysis of NPK in grain and straw was carried out on the sample of yield components. In saline field studies were also analyzed the total absorption of Na in grain and straw.

The data were analyzed by ANOVA and HSD test. Correlation and regression techniques (both simple and multiple regression) were used to observe interaction among the variables.. Comparative studies were conducted on growth parameters, yield components and crop yields, as well as the development of soil salinity in the saline field.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results showed a significant effect of the main plot (amelioration) and subplot (varieties), while the interaction between the two factors was not significant on grain production. Table 1 shows the average grain yield (GKG) on the three levels.

The effectiveness of the ameliorations was shown by the significant differences between M1, M2 and M3. The soil amelioration (M2 and M3) provided significantly higher grain yields than without the technology (M1). The grain yield on M1 was only 2.33 tha⁻¹ while in M2 and M3 were 2.79 and 2.83 t ha⁻¹ dry grain yield, respectively. The significant difference was also shown in varieties. The highest dry grain yield was on Inpara-4 (3.42 tha⁻¹), followed by Inpara-2 (2.89 tha⁻¹), the lowest rice grain yield was produced by Sintanur (2.14

tha-1). It appears that the number of panicles and the number of grain plays a role in the grain yield since the difference in the number of panicles and the number of grains shows the same trend with the grain yield.

Table 1. Grain yield average (t/ha dry) at various levels of land amelioration and varieties tested in Tidal Swampy Areas of Simbur Naik Jambi, 2014

Treatments	Dry Yield (t/ha)	Number of Panicle	Number of grain		Grain emptiness (%)	Weight of 1000 grain (g)*
			Total	Fertil		
<i>Amelioration</i>						
M1	2,336 a	10,6 a	604 a	444 a	26,30 a	23,30 a
M2	2,790 b	10,7 a	659 a	475 a	27,47 a	23,35 a
M3	2,832 b	11,3 a	685 a	526 a	22,86 a	23,57 a
<i>Varieties</i>						
Sintanur	2,135 a	9,8 a	463 a	351 a	24,54 abc	24,72 d
Inpara 1	2,458 b	10,7 ab	670 b	463 b	30,32 c	23,50 bc
Inpara 2	2,885 c	11,8 b	662 b	469 b	28,93 bc	23,04 b
Inpara 4	3,418 d	11,2 ab	1024 c	782 c	23,87 ab	21,72 a
Inpara 5	2,369 ab	11,0 ab	427 a	343 a	20,06 a	24,04 cd

Alphabets on each lane and factor are followed by the same letters, meaning not significantly different in HSD test (honestly significant difference) 5%. * at 14% grain water content.

M1 showed the lowest grain yield, ranging between 1.87 t/ha (Sintanur) and 3.17 t/ha (Inpara-4). It was apparent that Inpara-4 had more adapted to tidal land conditions followed by Inpara-2. Drainage and lime treatments before planting have a positive effect on the grain yield (Dent1986). Charcoal adding with ZnSO₄ as M3 treatment had little effect on the increase of grain yield (FAO, 2005). The effect will be seen in the next crop planting season because of the residual effect of provided husk charcoal.

Drainage and lime treatment of Inpara-4 and Inpara-1 increased 0.38 t ha-1 (20%) and 0.80 t ha-1 (42%) of the grain yield, respectively. Thus, there was a different response in rice varieties to draining and calcification (although the interaction was not different significant)(Table 2 and Figure 1).

Table 2. Average of rice grain yield (t ha⁻¹) on amelioration and varieties treatments in Tidal swamp land in Simbur Naik Jambi, 2014

Varieties	Amelioration levels		
	M1	M2	M3
Sintanur	1,865	2,267	2,274
Inpara 1	1,897	2,701	2,775
Inpara 2	2,590	3,017	3,046
Inpara 4	3,167	3,546	3,543
Inpara 5	2,163	2,419	2,524

Figure 1. Average grain yield (ton / ha GKG) at various levels of amelioration and varieties tested in tidal land SimburNaik Jambi, 2014

In the correlation matrix showed relationship between grain yield and yield components (Table 3), the total grain number, grain quantity and 1000 grains weight of grain contents were correlate closely with total grain yield. The highest correlation was between total grain and grain content ($r = 0.98$).

Table 3. Correlation matrix between average of grain yield (g/plot dry) with yield components in Tidal Swamp Simbur Naik Jambi, 2014

Variable	Y	X1	X2	X3	X4	X5
Y	1,0000	-	-	-	-	-
X1	0,3344	1,0000	-	-	-	-
X2	0,7179	0,2567	1,0000	-	-	-
X3	0,7353	0,2481	0,9779	1,0000	-	-
X4	-0,0680	0,0544	0,1200	-0,0809	1,0000	-
X5	-0,6953	-0,3710	-0,6517	-0,6127	-0,2355	1,0000

Note:

Y = Dry weight result (t / ha)

X1 = number of panicles / clumps

X2 = total grain number / clump

n = 45

X3 = number of grain content / clump

X4 = empty grain (%)

X5 = weight of 1000 grains of grain content (g)

The study also found that the most significant component of grain yield was total grain quantity (X2), grain emptiness (X4), and weight of 1000 grains of grain content (X5) with multiple regression equations as follows:

$$Y = 7455 + 1,001^{**} X2 - 21,109^{*} X4 - 209,92^{**} X5$$

(R² = 0,6550; F-hitung = 25,95; n = 45)

At each observation, there was no significant difference for plant height with ameliorant levels. However, the visual performance for rice morphology showed a higher appearance; including the average of plant height at harvesting time at M3 treatment (= 93 cm) compared with the treatment of M1 and M2 were about 88 cm. Since 35 DAP, there has been a noticeable difference in plant height between varieties. Inpara-5 showed shorter of plant high (= 81 cm) than other varieties (Table 4).

Table 4. Average of plant height at various land amelioration levels and varieties tested in Tidal Swampy area in Simbur Naik, Jambi, 2014

Treatments	Plant Hight (cm)			
	21 DAP	35 DAP	55 DAP	Harvesting
<i>Ameliorations</i>				
M1	41 a	57 a	76 a	89 a
M2	40 a	57 a	76 a	88 a
M3	43 a	58 a	77 a	93 a
<i>Varieties</i>				
Sintanur	45 a	57 b	87 c	91 b
Inpara 1	41 a	57 b	75 b	94 b
Inpara 2	41 a	58 b	73 ab	92 b
Inpara 4	39 a	56 ab	70 a	91 b
Inpara 5	41 a	54 a	78 b	81 a

The numbers in each row (varieties) are followed by the same letter, which is not significantly different in the HSD test (honestly significant difference) 5%.

The average of tillers number (Table 5) was no difference significant, although the M3 treatment tended to show a high number of tillers in each observation as well as to the plant height. Since 35 DAP has seen a significant difference in the number of tillers/clumps between varieties. Inpara-2 and Inpara-4 produced a high number of tillering than others.

Table 5. Average number of tillers per hill at various levels of soil amelioration and varieties tested in tidal swampy areas in Simbur Naik Jambi, 2014

Treatments	Average number of tillers per hill			
	21 DAP	35 DAP	55 DAP	Clumps
<i>Amelioration</i>				
M1	10,1 a	9,9 a	12,7 a	10,6 a
M2	10,2 a	9,7 a	13,2 a	10,7 a
M3	11,3 a	10,6 a	13,3 a	11,3 a
<i>Varieties</i>				
Sintanur	10,4 a	9,6 a	12,7 a	9,8 a
Inpara 1	10,6 a	10,2 bc	12,9 a	10,7 ab
Inpara 2	10,7 a	10,7 c	13,1 ab	11,8 b
Inpara 4	10,7 a	10,1 b	13,9 b	11,2 ab
Inpara 5	10,2 a	9,9 ab	12,8 a	11,0 ab

Note: The numbers in each row (varieties) are followed by the same letter, which is not significantly different in the HSD test (honestly significant difference) 5%.

There was a significant interaction effect between amelioration and varieties on the number of tillers/clumps at 35 DAP (Table 6). For rice varieties

treatment, it appeared that amelioration has no effect to increase in the number of tillers, except in Inpara-5, the number of tillers increased at the M3 treatment as 2 tillers/bundles.

Table 6. Average number of 35 DAP tillers (stems/clumps) on amelioration and varieties treatment in Tidal Swampy Areas in Simbur Naik, Jambi, 2014

Varieties	Amelioration levels		
	M1	M2	M3
Sintanur	9,0 a	9,3 a	10,3 a
Inpara 1	10,3 a	10,0 a	10,3 a
Inpara 2	11,0 a	10,0 a	11,0 a
Inpara 4	10,3 a	10,0 a	10,0 a
Inpara 5	9,0 a	9,3 a	11,3 b

The numbers in each row (varieties) are followed by the same letter, which is not significantly different in the HSD test (honestly significant difference) 5%.

CONCLUSIONS

Several rice varieties had already tested in Jambi tidal swampy areas and showed different response on grain yield. The highest grain yield was Inpara-4 (3.42 tha⁻¹ of dry grain yield), followed by Inpara-2 (2.89 tha⁻¹). Inpara-1 showed higher response to plant high in improved tidal swampy land. Land amelioration could improve the growth of rice, however, the supply of charcoal husk and the addition of ZnSO₄ have no effect on tidal rice production.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

Thank you to Dr. Anischan Gani who has provided guidance from the beginning of the research to the writing of this paper.

REFERENCES

- Alihamsyah T. 2005. Pengembangan Lahan Rawa Lebak untuk Usaha Pertanian, Balai Penelitian Pertanian Lahan Rawa, Banjarbaru, 53 p
- Bahar FA. 2003. Pengembangan tanaman padi berkelanjutan, Jilid 1 *Dalam*. Prosiding Konferensi Nasional XVI HIGI, SEAMEO BIOTROP, Bogor, p, 12–19.
- Dent D. 1986. Acid Sulphate Soils. a Baseline for Research and Development, International Institute for Land Reclamation Improvement/ILRI, A,A Wageningen, The Netherlands, Publication 39, p, 22–36, 43–46, 74–77,

- Erfandi D. 2009. Identifikasi dan Delineasi Tingkat Salinitas dan Reaksi Tanah Akibat Intrusi Air Laut pada Areal Persawahan di Pantura, Jawa Barat, Laporan Hasil Penelitian Balai Penelitian Tanah, Bogor,
- Fagi AM, and I Las. 2007. Menggali potensi pengembangan pertanian pada lahan rawa . Pengalaman masa lalu dan strategi ke depan, *Dalam*. Mukhlis, M, Noor, A, Supriyo, I, Noor, dan R,S, Simatupang (Ed.). Prosiding Seminar Nasional Pertanian Lahan Rawa “Revitalisasi Kawasan PLG dan Lahan Rawa Lainnya untuk Membangun Lumbung Pangan Nasional”, Kuala Kapuas, 3–4 Agustus 2007, Buku I, p, 49–61,
- FAO, 2005. 20 Things to Know About. The Impact of Salt Water on Agricultural Land in Aceh Province, FAO field guide, United Nations Food and Agriculture Organization, FAO, March 2005
- Gain P MA, Mannan PS, Pal M, Maheb H, and ParvinS. 2004. Effect of Salinity on Some Yield Attributes of Rice, *Pakistan Journal of Biological Sciences* 7 (5). 760-762,
- Najib M, and Arifin F. 2010. Peningkatan hasil padi di lahan rawa sulfat masam dengan pemupukan fosfat dan perbaikan varietas, *Dalam* Inovasi Teknologi Padi untuk Mempertahankan Swasembada dan Mendorong Ekspor Beras, Prosiding Seminar Nasional Hasil Penelitian Padi 2009 (S, Abdurachman, H,M, Toha dan A, Gani Eds,) p. 929-941
- Notohadiprawiro T. 2000. Tanah dan Lingkungan, Cetakan ke-2, Pusat Studi Sumberdaya Lahan (PPSL) Universitas Gadjah Mada, Yogyakarta, 187p,
- Nugroho K, Alkushima, Paidi W, Ahdini, Abdurrahman H, Suhardjo, andWidjaya-Adhi, IPG,1992. Peta areal potensial untuk pengembangan pertanian lahan rawa pasang surut, rawa dan pantai, Proyek Penelitian Sumber Daya Lahan, Pusat Penelitian Tanah dan Agroklimat, Badan Penelitian dan Pengembangan Pertanian Departemen Pertanian,
- Raihan S, Ar-Riza I, Fauziati N, and Hairani A, 2002. Teknologi peningkatan efisiensi produksi tanaman di lahan rawa, *Dalam*. Laporan Akhir Tahun Bagian Proyek Penelitian Sumberdaya Lahan, Balai Penelitian Pertanian Lahan Rawa, 72p,
- Rhoades JD, Manteghi NA, Shouse PJ, and AlvesWJ. 1989. Soil electrical conductivity and soil salinity; New Formulations and Calibrations, *Soil Sci, Soc, Am, J*, 53. 433-439,
- Sarwani M, M Noor, and Masganti, 1994. Potensi, Kendala dan Peluang Pasang Surut dalam Perspektif Pengembangan Tanaman Pangan, *Dalam*,

Pengelolaan Air dan Produktivitas Lahan Rawa Pasang Surut, Balai Penelitian Tanaman Pangan, Banjarbaru.

Sharma BR, and Minhas PS. 2005. Strategies for managing saline/alkali waters for sustainable agricultural production in South Asia, *Agricultural water management* 78. 136-151.

Simatupang RS, and Nurita, 2010. Teknologi olah tanah konservasi dan implementasinya dalam peningkatan produksi di lahan rawa pasang surut, *Dalam Inovasi Teknologi Padi untuk Mempertahankan Swasembada dan Mendorong Ekspor Beras, Prosiding Seminar Nasional Hasil Penelitian Padi 2009* (S, Abdulrachman, H,M, Toha dan A, Gani Eds,) p. 863-875

Watson GA and M Willis, 1994. Farmer's local and traditional rice crop protection techniques. some examples from coastal swamplands, Kalimantan, Indonesia, *IARD Journal* 7 (1 & 2). 25-30